

Fear, Anxiety, and Cyberchondria during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Emotional and Behavioural Responses in the Adult Population

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The present study aimed to explore the prevalence and severity of fear, anxiety and cyberchondria in the adult population and to know their interrelatedness, after the COVID-19 pandemic. The ability of the internet to spread information quickly has had a number of advantages like enabling people to assess and prepare for the associated threat. However, due to COVID-19 uncertainties around sickness and death, and the abundance of information, the need to search for health-related information has increased, primarily to eliminate anxiety and fear of COVID-19. The study was carried out on a general population sample of 101, within the age range 18-60, of Indian origin. The data was collected using GAD-7 scale, the Fear of Covid-19 Scale and the Cyberchondria Severity Scale CSS-12. Results revealed a significant positive correlation between the three variables; significant gender differences were found in fear of COVID-19.

Keywords: COVID-19, generalised anxiety, cyberchondria

The word cyberchondria is a combination of "cyber" and "hypochondriasis," and it refers to the intensification of health-related anxiety caused by frequent online searches for medical information (Recupero, 2010). During the COVID-19 pandemic, several factors contributed to the development of cyberchondria: (i) increased fear and perception of threat from a novel and less understood illness; (ii) challenge in coping with the unpredictability encircling the pandemic; (iii) the lack of clear, trustworthy, and authoritative documentation of statistics and facts; (iv) difficulties in handling an overwhelming amount of data that is often contradictory, confusing, unverified, and frequently changing, combined with a reduced ability to filter irrelevant details; and (e) the inability of repeated online searches for health information to deliver meaningful comfort or clear answers (Starcevic et al., 2020). "Fear is described as an unpleasant emotional state that typically arises when an individual perceives something as a threat" (de Hoog et al., 2008). Schimmenti et al. (2020) explain that fear experienced during the COVID-19 pandemic can be viewed through four interrelated psycho-physiological aspects:

Bodily Dimension: This refers to fear directed at one's own body, including concerns about its vulnerability and safety.

Interpersonal Dimension: This involves fear connected to close relationships, such as worrying about loved ones or fearing they may pose a risk.

Behavioural Dimension: This includes anxiety around making decisions-being afraid to act, but also fearful of inaction.

Cognitive Dimension: This covers the fear of acquiring potentially distressing information, as well as the fear of staying uninformed.

Generalized Anxiety Disorder (GAD) is marked by ongoing and overwhelming worry that lasts for at least several months (ICD-11). People with GAD may show symptoms including constant nervousness, tiredness, irritability, muscle tightness, trouble focusing, sleep disturbances, a racing heart, breathing difficulties, excessive sweating, and light-headedness. This disorder is typically linked to feelings of fear or unease in response to actual or imagined dangers, uncertainty, or a sense of being exposed or at risk (WHO, 2016).

During the first and second waves of the COVID-19 pandemic, levels of fear, anxiety, and health-related online searching behaviour rose significantly across populations. The extraordinary circumstances surrounding the pandemic, including abrupt disruptions to daily routines, restrictions on mobility, and uncertainty about the future, adversely affected psychological well-being (Galea et al., 2020). The pervasive sense of threat and unpredictability made it difficult for individuals to regulate emotions and manage distress effectively. Consequently, frequent online searches for health information, intended to reduce uncertainty, often had the opposite effect, intensifying anxiety and reinforcing maladaptive checking behaviours (Fofana et al., 2020; Jokić-Begić et al., 2020).

These observations suggest that fear of COVID-19 may be closely linked with cyberchondria and generalized anxiety, both of which share cognitive and emotional components related to uncertainty intolerance and perceived vulnerability. Accordingly, the present study was conceptualized on the assumption that COVID-related

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fear could be associated with higher levels of cyberchondria and generalized anxiety among individuals.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the association between Cyberchondria, Generalised Anxiety Disorder and Fear of Covid-19 on the general Indian population.
- To determine the impact of GAD severity on Fear of Covid-19 and Cyberchondria.
- To compare two genders (Male & Female) on Fear of COVID-19, GAD, and Cyberchondria.

Hypotheses of the Study

- It is expected that there will be a positive association between Generalized Anxiety and Fear of COVID-19
- It is expected that there will be a positive association between Cyberchondria and Fear of COVID-19
- It is expected that there will be a positive association between Cyberchondria and Generalized Anxiety
- It is expected that women will experience more anxiety than men.
- It is expected that women will experience more fear of Covid 19 than men.

Method

Participants

The sample consisted of 101 participants (43 males & 58 females) from the general population of an Indian setting. The age range was 18-60. They all belong to the middle or upper-middle socio-economic stratum. All of them had completed their graduation, and most of them were post-graduates. They were approached through psychosocial support groups on social media. An online survey was conducted using GAD-7, CSS-12, and the Fear of COVID-19 questionnaire.

Measures

The data was collected using the following inventories:

Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7 Scale (GAD-7) is a 7-item, self-rated scale developed by Spitzer, Kroenke, Williams, and Löwe (2006) as a screening tool and severity indicator for GAD 7. Internal consistency was good ($\alpha = 0.89$). The GAD-7 has demonstrated good psychometric properties, including sensitivity (89%) and specificity (82%) for diagnosing GAD. The scale has demonstrated excellent reliability ($\alpha = .92$) and validity (construct validity with Beck Anxiety Inventory ($r = 0.72$)) for assessing generalized anxiety symptoms in both clinical and general populations (Spitzer et al., 2006).

The Fear of COVID-19 Scale is a seven-item scale. The participants indicate their level of agreement with the statements using a five-item Likert-type scale. It is reliable (internal consistency ($\alpha = .82$), test-retest reliability (ICC = .72) and valid ($r = 0.511$) in assessing fear of COVID-19 among the general population (Ahorsu et al., 2020).

The Cyberchondria Severity Scale (CSS-12) is a brief measure of worry/anxiety attributable to excessive online health research developed by McElroy and Shevlin (2014). The Cronbach's alpha for the total scale was 0.94, indicating high overall internal reliability.

Procedure

Data were collected through an online survey using purposive

snowball sampling. A Google Form link containing the study details, objectives, inclusion criteria, and informed consent statement was disseminated through social media platforms and psychosocial support groups. Participants aged 18-60 years, with at least graduate-level education and residing in India, were invited to participate voluntarily. Before beginning the survey, each participant provided informed consent electronically, acknowledging their voluntary participation and the right to withdraw at any stage without consequence. The survey included standardised tools, specifically the GAD-7, Cyberchondria Severity Scale12, and Fear of COVID-19 Scale. Anonymity and confidentiality were maintained throughout. Ethical clearance for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee of the Post-Graduate Institute of Behavioural and Medical Sciences (PGIBAMS), Raipur, before data collection. All procedures adhered to the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki (2013).

Statistical Analysis

In explorative analysis, measures of central tendency, such as mean and standard deviation, were carried out to study the nature and distribution of scores on various variables. Analysis of Variance and t-ratio was carried out.

Results

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Variable	N	N
Age	18-33 (N = 61)	34-62 (N = 40)
Gender	M (N=43)	F (N=58)
Marital Status	Married (N=41)	Unmarried (N=60)
Education	Post Grad. (N=40)	Graduate or less (N=61)
Income	Avg. 8lac p.a.	

Note. Avg.=Average; p.a= Per annum

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics of Study Variables (GAD, Fear of COVID-19, & Cyberchondria)

Variables	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. GAD 7	101	.00	21.00	5.46	5.111
2. Fear of Covid-19	101	7.00	30.00	16.67	5.381
3. Cyberchondria Severity	101	12.00	45.00	26.09	7.689

Note. GAD-7 = Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7 item scale.

Table 3

Correlation Matrix between Cyberchondria, GAD, and Fear of COVID-19

Variables	Cyberchondria	GAD	Fear of COVID-19
Cyberchondria	-	273**	300**
GAD		-	270*
Fear of COVID-19			-

Note. * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.01$, GAD= Generalized Anxiety Disorder

30.6% of the participants had mild GAD, 13.7% had moderate levels of GAD, and 9.7% had severe GAD levels.

Table 4

Mean Scores of Fear of COVID-19 and Cyberchondria across Levels of GAD Severity

Variables	Levels of GAD	f	Mean Scores
Fear of Covid-19	Normal	34	14.59
	Mild	38	18.21
	Moderate	17	17.29
	Severe	12	16.83
	Total	101	16.67
Cyberchondria	Normal	34	23.26
	Mild	38	27.84
	Moderate	17	28.05
	Severe	12	25.83
	Total	101	26.09

Note. GAD= Generalized Anxiety Disorder

Table 5

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Showing Impact of GAD Severity on Fear of COVID-19 and Cyberchondria

I.V. GAD		df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Fear of COVID-19	Between groups	3	81.49	2.98*	0.035
	Within Groups	97	27.33		
	Total	100			
Cyberchondria Severity	Between Groups	3	151.57	2.694	0.05
	Within groups	97	56.27		
	Total	100			

Note. * $p < 0.05$

Analysis of Variance

Analysis of variance revealed that there was a significant impact on fear of COVID-19 across the four GAD categories: normal, mild, moderate, and severe. Post hoc analysis (t-test) revealed that people with mild severity of GAD had significantly higher Fear of Covid-19 than those with normal GAD levels.

Table 6

Gender Differences in Fear of COVID-19, GAD, and Cyberchondria

Variables	t-test	Mean difference F
Fear of Covid-19	2.53*	66
G.A.D 7	.93	.95
Cyberchondria	1.610	2.482.

Note. * $p < 0.05$

There was a significant difference between males and females on Fear of Covid-19, females ($M = 17.77$) having more fear than males ($M = 15.11$).

Discussion

The present study examined the relationship between generalized anxiety, cyberchondria, and fear of COVID-19 among Indian adults. Findings revealed significant positive correlations among all three variables, suggesting that higher anxiety levels were associated with greater fear and increased health-related online searches. This supports earlier findings that anxiety amplifies health vigilance and may lead to excessive information seeking during uncertain times

(Jungmann & Witthöft, 2020; Starcevic et al., 2020).

Fear of COVID-19 significantly varied across GAD severity levels, indicating that even mild anxiety heightened fear responses. However, GAD severity did not significantly affect cyberchondria, implying that online health-seeking may be influenced by other factors such as digital habits or health anxiety traits (van Kessel et al., 2023). Gender analysis showed females experienced greater fear of COVID-19, consistent with global patterns of higher emotional reactivity among women (Biswas & Biswas, 2021). Anxiety symptoms were found to have differed by gender in Pappa et al.'s (2020) study during the Covid period. It was emphasized by Liu et al. (2020) that the pandemic caused higher stress and anxiety in females than males. Nino et al. (2021) study showed that women are generally more likely to have a fear of COVID-19 than men.

Overall, the findings highlight a reinforcing cycle where fear fuels anxiety and drives health-related searches that, instead of reducing worry, may worsen it. Promoting accurate online health information and psychological resilience is crucial in managing pandemic-related distress and preventing maladaptive digital behaviours.

Conclusion

The findings indicate that generalized anxiety significantly influences fear of COVID-19 and is positively associated with cyberchondria. These results underscore the need for responsible online health communication that emphasizes clarity, accuracy, and solution-focused information to reduce uncertainty and promote reassurance in the general population.

Limitations of the Study

The study used purposive online sampling, limiting representativeness across regions and socioeconomic groups. Self-reported data may involve response bias. The cross-sectional design restricts causal inference, and the small sample size limits generalizability. Findings are context-specific to the COVID-19 period and may not extend to other health crises.

References

- Ahorsu, D. K., Lin, C. Y., Imani, V., Saffari, M., Griffiths, M. D., & Pakpour, A. H. (2022). The Fear of COVID-19 Scale: Development and Initial Validation. *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction*, 20, 1537-1545.
- Biswas, R. K., & Biswas, A. (2021). Gender differences in emotional reactivity during the COVID-19 pandemic: Evidence from global data. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 632.
- Fofana, M., Patil, R., & Vasquez, D. (2020). The psychological impact of COVID-19: A global survey. *Journal of Global Health*, 10(2), 159-167. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43076-022-00227-x>
- Galea, S., Merchant, R. M., & Lurie, N. (2020). The mental health consequences of COVID-19 and physical distancing: The need for prevention and early intervention. *JAMA Internal Medicine*, 180, 6.
- Jokic-Begic, N., Smaic, M., & Krizan, V. (2020). The impact of COVID-19 pandemic on anxiety and behavior: A study on cyberchondria. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 74, 102324.
- Jungmann, S. M., & Witthöft, M. (2020). Health anxiety, cyberchondria, and coping in the current COVID-19 pandemic: Which factors are related to coronavirus anxiety? *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 73, Article 102239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.janxdis.2020.102239>
- Liu, N., Zhang, F., Wei, C., Jia, Y., Shang, Z., Sun, L., Wu, L., Sun, Z., Zhou, Y., Wang, Y., & Liu, W. (2020). Prevalence and predictors of PTSS during COVID-19 outbreak in China: Comparison between females and males. *Psychiatry Research*, 287, 112921.
- McElroy, E., & Shevlin, M. (2014). The development and initial validation of the Cyberchondria Severity Scale (CSS). *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 28(2), 259-265. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.janxdis.2013.12.007>

- Niño, M., Harris, C., Drawve, G., & Fitzpatrick, K. M. (2021). Gender differences in fear of COVID-19. *Health Education and Behavior, 48*(2), 159-166. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1090198120988395>
- Pappa, S., Ntella, V., Giannakas, T., Giannakoulis, V. G., Papoutsis, E., & Katsaounou, P. (2020). Prevalence of depression, anxiety, and insomnia among healthcare workers during the COVID-19 pandemic: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Brain, Behavior, and Immunity, 88*, 901-907.
- Recupero, P. R. (2010). The mental status of the Internet. *Journal of the American Academy of Psychiatry and the Law, 38*(3), 392-398.
- Starcevic, V., Schimmenti, A., Billieux, J., & Berle, D. (2020). Cyberchondria in the time of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Human Behavior and Emerging Technologies, 2*(4), 283-291. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbe2.233>
- van Kessel, R., Kyriopoulos, I., Wong, B., & Mossialos, E. (2023). The effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on digital health-seeking behavior: Big data interrupted time-series analysis of google trends. *Journal of Medical Internet Research, 25*, e42401.
- Wang, C., Pan, R., Wan, X., Tan, Y., Xu, L., McIntyre, R.S., Choo, F.N., Tran, B., Ho, R., Sharma, V.K., & Ho, C. (2020b). A longitudinal study on the mental health of general population during the COVID-19 epidemic in China. *Brain, Behavior, and Immunity, 87*, 40-48.
- World Health Organization (2016). *ICD-10-CM: International classification of diseases, clinical modification* (10th revision). <https://icd.who.int/>

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